

Evaluation of the Performance of the Operational Division on Customer Satisfaction at Pt. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021

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Abstract:- Evaluation of employee coordination and operational performance during productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyer) are determining factors toward customer satisfaction. As such, there are necessary efforts to increase productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyer). The research was conducted in PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin with sample amounting to 100 employees. Data was gathered through instrument in form with tested. Likert scale. . . The used. data. analysis. method. is. path. analysis. . First research result found that employee coordination has positive and significant correlation towards productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyer). Therefore, it can be concluded that operational performance has positive and significant correlation towards productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyer). Relevant employee coordination and operational performance in productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyer) has effects to increase customer satisfaction, thus productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyer) as intervening variable is proved to improve employee coordination and operational performance towards customer satisfaction.

Keywords:- Employee Coordination, Operational Performance, Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyer), Customer Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The improvement in the company's performance gives rise to the need to re-evaluate the results that have been achieved in the previous period. By re-evaluating the results that have been achieved, input can be obtained in the form of information about the company's internal and external constraints that hinder the achievement of performance improvement. One of the ways to achieve the company's goals is the good performance of Human Resources in the company as well as work support tools to more effectively achieve the company's goals, this applies to all business fields including business in the logistics sector and loading and unloading companies.

PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa is a subsidiary of PT. Adaro Energy, Tbk. which is engaged in energy, while for PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa serves Adaro Logistics in Kelanis by carrying out various shipping administration activities such as scheduling the entry and exit of barges, loading and unloading coal to and from barges. For this matter PT. The Harapan of Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin and customers can assess and know where the success obtained by the cargo loading and unloading activity process that has been trusted to carry it out is in accordance with the requests and schedules that have been informed in order to facilitate the production process or other activities at the destination of cargo owned by PT customers. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin. In this case PT. It is Harapand that Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin will get customer satisfaction with measuring instruments from several dimensions, namely, consisting of the suitability of service quality, marketing, and also product prices.

Coal loading and unloading activities carried out by PT. Bahtera Internusa Harapans become vital to support the business of PT. Adaro Energy itself with the acquisition of PT. Maritime Mighty Barito. This is a concern, especially on the performance of Human Resources and tools such as conveyors, because if the performance of human resources itself is poor, it will affect the productivity of supporting equipment for loading and unloading coal, this will cause a decrease in customer trust. The problem that is often faced is the unpreparedness of the conveyer and loading and unloading equipment when it will be used, this will result in late delivery which will decrease the company's image, second is the ineffectiveness of coal loading time to barges, third is the routine maintenance of conveyers and other coal loading and unloading support equipment that does not run as it should where this will reduce performance, fourth is the frequent occurrence of damage to the conveyer and other loading support equipment which will affect the non-achievement of timeliness of coal distribution to customers and the decrease in the productivity of the tool, fifth is the factor of inadequate field conditions where the coal loading place is still not like other docks, the sixth is the uneven coordination of operational employees when loading coal this will resulting in errors in the loading and unloading of coal to and from barges. These things will be addressed if supported by skilled human resources and of course skilled human resources will produce better performance in the company and still maintain good productivity of loading and unloading equipment.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This study tries to answer the following questions:

- Whether there is an influence of operational employee coordination has a direct effect on the productivity of PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021?
- Whether there is an influence on the performance of operational employees has a direct effect on the productivity of PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021?
- Whether there is an influence of operational employee coordination has a direct effect on customer satisfaction of PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021?
- Whether there is an influence on the performance of operational employees has a direct effect on the customer satisfaction of PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021?
- Whether there is an influence on the productivity of operational employees has a direct effect on customer satisfaction of PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021?
- Is there an indirect influence of operational employee coordination on customer satisfaction through the productivity of PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021?
- Is there an indirect influence of operational employee performance on customer satisfaction through the productivity of PT. Harapan Bahtera Internusa Banjarmasin in 2021?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Employee Coordination*

Coordination is the process of integrating goals and activities in separate units in an organization to achieve organizational goals efficiently, Yohannes Yahya (2006: 95). According to George R. Terry quoted by Hasibuan (2007: 85) coordination is a synchronous and orderly effort to provide the right amount and time, and direct the implementation to produce a uniform and harmonious action on a predetermined goal. Meanwhile, according to E.F.L. Brech quoted by Hasibuan (2007: 85) coordination is to balance and move the team by providing a suitable location of work activities to each of them and keeping the activities carried out with proper harmony between the members themselves.

According to Hasibuan, In Manulang, 2002, employees are sellers of services "mind or energy" and receive compensation whose amount has been determined in advance.

According to Subri, In Manulang, 2002, Employees are residents of working age "aged 15-64 years" or the total number of residents in a country that produce goods and services if there is a permit for their labor, and if they are willing to participate in such activities.

Based on the description above, the synthesis of employee coordination is a cooperation formed between units of an organization to create a uniform and harmonious action in achieving common goals.

➤ *Operational Performance*

According to (Hasan et al., 2017) Company performance is the result of a management activity in a company. From the results of this performance, it is used as a benchmark parameter in assessing the success of the company's management itself, the company's performance is none other than being deployed from internal company control. More and more small, large and even medium-sized enterprises and developing each other. Some companies very intensely monitor how the performance of a company is developing as well as the division of duties and responsibilities, company performance is something that is produced by the company in a certain period and refers to the established standards. The distribution of company performance can be measured by financial and non-financial measures. Non-financial performance measures include customer satisfaction, productivity and cost effectiveness.

In a journal excerpt (Hasan et al., 2017), states the benefits of performance for organizations include:

- a. Adapting organizational goals to the goals of the team and individuals.
- b. Improving performance increases commitment, supports core values.
- c. Improve the training and development process.
- d. Improve the basis of training and continuous development.
- e. Working on a career planning base
- f. Help restrain skilled workers from moving.
- g. Support total quality initiatives and customer service and service.
- h. Support cultural change.

According to (Adham, 2019) the notion of operations is an abstract concept to facilitate the measurement of a variable. Or operational can be interpreted as a guideline in carrying out an activity or research work. Operational definitions according to the observed characteristics to define or change concepts that are constructive with words describing a behavior or symptom that is observed, tested and determined its correctness to others.

According to Asep Hermawan (2015) in a journal citation (Adham, 2019) The notion of operations is an explanation of how we can measure variables. These measurements can be done with numbers or certain attributes.

According to (Heizer and Render, 2014) Operations is the set of activities value in the form of goods and services by transforming inputs into outputs cited in the journal (Pribadi et al., 2017)

In the journal excerpt (Ananto, 2016) operational performance comes from the word performance (performance). As stated by Mangkunegara (2009) that the term operational performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (work performance or actual achievements achieved by a person) namely the results of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. So according to Mangkunegara (2009), work performance or achievement is the result of quality and

quantity work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

According to (Ratnasari, 2015) operational performance is one of the main factors to achieve company goals, if the performance of operational employees is poor, productivity in the company will also decrease and vice versa. In order to create the expected performance, a company represented from the management must be able to create a conducive work environment and be sensitive to the conditions of employees in the company. Each company will strive to always improve the performance of its employees in order to achieve the goals that have been set by the company.

In accordance with the explanation above operational performance is a job given to a person in carrying out tasks on the basis of speed, experience, and time, these results can be measured because the operational performance results from several dimensions owned, namely, organizational goals, improving processes, and also quality initiatives measured variables in numbers and with certain attribute attributes.

➤ *Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor)*

As shown by (Tri Hernawati, 2018), Productivity is the proportion of how well it is able to utilize assets in achieving ideal results. The results obtained are identified with feasibility in achievement. While the assets used are characterized by proficiency in getting the most maximum results by using assets minimally. Viability is centered around results, and adequacy is how much of the result is from the contribution of existing assets. Or again it can be said how successfully current assets are used to deliver predetermined results. As a rule, usefulness is regularly characterized as a proficient utilization of assets to create results. Productivity is an element of proficiency and survival, with the aim that exercises completed productively and adequately in the utilization of assets including materials, money and time will provide efficiency with high value.

Furthermore, as stated by (Panjaitan, 2017), Productivity is a form of idea that describes the relationship between the results (administration submitted and the amount of merchandise) and the source (size of work, land, capital, and so on). Productivity is expressly identified with how far an interaction results by devouring a particular data source. Productivity is the proportion between information and results with due regard to subsequent results, usually a mixture can be used to create a certain level of yield. Productivity is the proportion of how useful a cycle is to give results.

On the basis of the explanation as mentioned, it is quite possible to feel that productivity has 3 important components. First of all, it is specifically the feasibility that is used as the value of accuracy in choosing a way to do something to achieve the goal. Second, it is able to be useful for assessing accuracy in getting things done by saving existing assets. Thirdly, it is in particular the quality that will make it clear how far the level of satisfaction is from the various determinations, prerequisites and assumptions of the client.

➤ *Customer Satisfaction*

Citations in journals (Fauzi, 2018) according to Kotler, Armstrong, and Opresnik (2017) cited in the journal (Fauzi, 2018) state that customer satisfaction is how the quality of the products produced by the company matches customer expectations. In detail, if the details of the resulting product are far from the expectations of consumers, it means that consumers are dissatisfied. If the product meets the customer's expectations, the customer is satisfied. Then if the product quality is more than the customer's expectations, the customer is satisfied. In addition, customer satisfaction becomes the main goal of the company when they deliver products or services. In addition, customer satisfaction can drive companies to achieve customer retention, market share, and profitability gains (Rust and Zahorik, 1993).

According to (Mardika, 2013) quoted in the journal (Waluyo, 2018) customer satisfaction is a level where the needs, desires, and expectations of customers are met which will result in repurchases or continued loyalty. The higher the quality of the products and services provided, the higher the satisfaction felt by customers. If customer satisfaction is as high, it can cause benefits for the business entity.

In the journal excerpt (Ratnasari, 2015) customer satisfaction is the level of a person's feeling as a result of a comparison between reality and expectations received from a product and service can the product's performance is much lower than customer expectations, the buyer is not satisfied if the performance meets expectations or exceeds expectations, the buyer feels satisfied or feels very happy. Customers generally expect products in the form of goods or services consumed to be accepted and enjoyed in good and satisfying service. Customer satisfaction can be evaluated, where the reception of the performance of the selected product / service meets customer expectations, in evaluating customer satisfaction a product always refers to the attributes that form satisfaction (Dukta, 2005) that universally, the attributes of customer satisfaction are:

- Attributes related to the product
- Service-related attributes
- Attributes related to purchase

Consumer satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment of a person, which comes from a comparison between his impressions of the performance or results of a good and service with the expectation of his expectations (Kotler, 2005: 36) in journal citations (Rahmatina et al., 2016). The factors that drive customer satisfaction (Hendy Irawan Juwandi, 2004: 37) are as follows:

- Product quality, customers will be satisfied if after buying and using the product it turns out that the quality of the product is good.
- Price, for sensitive customers, usually low prices are an important source of satisfaction because customers will get high value for money.
- Service quality, satisfaction with the quality of service in general is difficult to imitate. Service quality is a driver that has many dimensions, one of which is popular is service quality.

- Emotional Factor, customers will feel satisfied (proud) because of the emotional value provided by the brand of the product.
- Cost and convenience, customers will be more satisfied if it is relatively easy, comfortable and efficient in obtaining products or services.

In this study, in promoting customer satisfaction, companies should consider the four dimensions of mobile application electronic service quality, namely information quality, application design, payment methods, and security and privacy. Customer satisfaction can be measured in several dimensions of customer satisfaction consisting of the suitability of service quality, marketing, and also the price of the products provided.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

According to (Sugiyono, 2019) Non Probability Sampling is a technique that does not provide equal opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample. The Non Probability Sampling technique chosen is by saturated sampling (census), which is a sampling method when all members of the population are used as samples. This is often done when the population is small, less than 30 people.

In this study, the sample that will be taken is the entire PPIC shipping staff of PT. Maritime Barito Perkasa PT. Bukit Enim Energi, PT. Bhakti Energi Persada and, PT. Mustika Indah Permai is 25 employees per company with a total of 100 employees. The saturated sample method is a sample determination technique when all members of the population are used to be sampled.

V. RESULT

➤ *Validity Test*

The critical limit value of validity is 0.197. If the correlation value or calculated r is less than or less than 0.197 then the questionnaire item is declared invalid. Conversely, if the calculated value of r is greater than 0.197 then the questionnaire item is declared valid.

The following are the results of the validity test of the research instrument (questionnaire) for each of the variables studied:

Table 1. Validity Test Result

Pernyataan	Nilai Koefisien Koreksi (r hitung)				Status
	Koordinasi Karyawan Operasional (X1)	Kinerja Operasional (X2)	Produktifitas Alat Bongkar Muat Batu Bara (Conveyor) (Y)	Kepuasan Pelanggan (Z)	
No. 1	0.803	0.866	0.611	0.883	Valid
No. 2	0.673	0.709	0.886	0.896	Valid
No. 3	0.603	0.810	0.898	0.880	Valid
No. 4	0.653	0.863	0.893	0.842	Valid
No. 5	0.898	0.931	0.871	0.887	Valid
No. 6	0.803	0.881	0.895	0.808	Valid

Source: Primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25.

Table 1 shows that each item of each of the variable questions of Operational Employee Coordination (X1), Operational Performance (X2), Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) (Y) and Customer Satisfaction (Z) is all declared valid.

➤ *Reliability Test*

Table 2. Reliability Test Result

Variable	Nilai Alpha	Nilai Batas	Status
Koordinasi Karyawan Operasional (X1)	0.833	0.70	Reliable
Kinerja Operasional (X2)	0.918	0.70	Reliable
Produktifitas Alat Bongkar Muat Batu Bara (Conveyor) (Y)	0.921	0.70	Reliable
Kepuasan Pelanggan (Z)	0.934	0.70	Reliable

Source: Primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Table 2 shows that the overall alpha value of the grains present in each variable is reliable, since the Cronbach Alpha coefficient is greater than 0.70.

From the results of the validity and reliability analysis mentioned above, overall the points of statement of each variable can be used and distributed to all respondents (100 Respondents), because each item shows valid and reliable results, then further analysis can be carried out.

➤ *Partial Test*

Table 3. Partial Test Structure 1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.008	2.419		2.070	.041
	Koordinasi Karyawan Operasional	.389	.097	.364	4.005	.000
	Kinerja Operasional	.409	.116	.321	3.534	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Produktifitas Conveyor

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

- Operational Employee Coordination (X1) affects the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) (Y). Showing the test results individually (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 less than 0.05 or [0.000 < 0.05] , then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, operational employee coordination has a positive and significant effect on the productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyor). The magnitude of the direct influence of Operational Employee Coordination on the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) is indicated by a Beta value of 0.364 or 36.4 percent.
- Operational Performance (X2) affects the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) (Y). Showing the test individually (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 less than 0.05 or [0.000 < 0.05] , then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment

(Conveyor). The magnitude of the effect of Operational Performance on the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) is indicated by a Beta value of 0.321 or 32.1 percent.

Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor).

Table 4. Partial Test Structure 2

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.482	1.600		.926	.357
	Koordinasi Karyawan Operasional	.383	.068	.395	5.648	.000
	Kinerja Operasional	.290	.080	.251	3.645	.000
	Produktifitas Conveyor	.333	.066	.367	5.073	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Pelanggan

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

- Operational Employee Coordination (X1) affects Customer Satisfaction (Z). Showing the individual (partial) test / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$, then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, Operational Employee Coordination has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. The magnitude of the direct influence of Operational Employee Coordination on Customer Satisfaction is indicated by a Beta value of 0.395 or 39.5 percent.
- Operational Performance (X2) affects Customer Satisfaction (Z) Showing the test individually (partial) / t test obtained Sig 0.000 less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$, then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. The magnitude of the effect of Operational Performance on Customer Satisfaction is indicated by a Beta value of 0.251 or 25.1 percent.
- The productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyor) (Y) affects Customer Satisfaction (Z). Showing the test individually (partial) / t test obtained a value of Sig value of 0.000 less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$, then the coefficient of path analysis is significant. Thus, the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. The magnitude of the influence of the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) on Customer Satisfaction is indicated by a Beta value of 0.367 or 36.7 percent.

➤ Sobel Test

Sobel test is a test to find out whether a relationship through a mediation variable is significantly able to function as a mediator in the relationship. To make it easier to calculate the z value of the sobel test, you can take advantage of the online danielsooper application through the www.danielsooper.com with the menu Statistic Calculator→Mediation Models → Sobel Test Calculator for Significance of Mediation, with the following results:

- Mediation Test The Effect of Operational Employee Coordination on Customer Satisfaction through the

Fig 1 Sobel test model 1

Based on Figure 1 shows a one-tailed probability of 0.00 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the Variable Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) can function as a mediator or be able to mediate the indirect influence of Operational Employee Coordination on Customer Satisfaction.

- Mediation Test the Effect of Operational Performance on Customer Satisfaction through the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor).

Fig 2. Sobel test model 2

Based on Figure 2, it shows a one-tailed probability of 0.00 < 0.05, so that it can be concluded that the Variable Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) can function as a mediator or be able to mediate the indirect influence of Operational Performance on Customer Satisfaction.

➤ Goodness of Fittest Test

Table 6. R Square Sub Structure 1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.574 ^a	.330	.316	1.081
a. Predictors: (Constant), Kinerja Operasional, Koordinasi Karyawan Operasional				

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Table 7. R Square Sub Structure 2

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.814 ^a	.663	.652	.699
a. Predictors: (Constant), Produktifitas Conveyor, Kinerja Operasional, Koordinasi Karyawan Operasional				

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Then the total diversity of data that can explain by the model is measured by:

$$R^2_m = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) \cdot (1 - R^2_2) \cdot (1 - R^2_p) \quad (1) \quad R^2_m = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) \cdot (1 - R^2_2) \cdot (1 - R^2_p) \quad (2)$$

$$= 1 - (0.330) \times (0.663) \quad (3)$$

$$R^2_m = 0.7760$$

The R²_m value of 0.7760 means that the diversity of data that can be described by the model is 77.60 percent, while the remaining 22.40 percent is explained by other variables outside the model. Thus the research model has a high predictive ability over the behavior of dependent variables characterized by a high coefficient of determination above 50 percent.

Fig 3: Path Analysis Result Diagram

VI. DISCUSSION

➤ **H1**, Operational Employee Coordination has a positive and significant effect on the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor). Based on the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the Operational Employee

Coordination variable path to the Productivity variable of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) was obtained was 0.364 or 36.4 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Coordination of Operational Employees, the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) will increase.

- **H2**, Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor). Based on the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the Operational Performance variable path was obtained against the Productivity variable of the Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor). is 0.321 or 32.1 percent with a significance of 0.001. This means that the better the Operational Performance, the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) will increase.
- **H3**, Operational Employee Coordination has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the Operational Employee Coordination variable path to the Customer Satisfaction variable was obtained by 0.395 or 39.5 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Operational Employee Coordination, the more Customer Satisfaction will increase.
- **H4**, Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the Operational Performance variable path to the Customer Satisfaction variable was obtained by 0.251 or 25.1 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Operational Performance, the more Customer Satisfaction will increase.
- **H5**, The Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the variable line coefficient of Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) to the Customer Satisfaction variable was obtained by 0.367 or 36.7 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyor), the customer satisfaction will increase.
- **H6**, The Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) is able to function as a mediator or mediate the influence of Operational Employee Coordination on Customer Satisfaction. This means that the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) that is appropriate for the Coordination of Operational Employees built by the company is able to increase Customer Satisfaction, so that the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) as an intervening variable is proven to serve to strengthen the influence of Operational Employee Coordination on Customer Satisfaction.
- **H7**, The Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) is able to function as a mediator or mediate the influence of Operational Performance on Customer Satisfaction. This means that the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) that is appropriate for operational performance built by the company is able to increase Customer Satisfaction, so that

the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) as an intervening variable is proven to serve to strengthen the influence of Operational Performance on Customer Satisfaction.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the results of research and overall analysis, some conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- Coordination of Operational Employees has a positive and significant effect on the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) PT. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin.
- Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) PT. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin.
- Operational Employee Coordination has a positive and significant effect on PT. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin.
- Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on PT. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin.
- The productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyor) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of PT. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin.
- The productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyor) is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect influence of Operational Employee Coordination on CUSTOMER SATISFACTION of PT. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin.
- The productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyor) is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect influence of Operational Performance on CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF PT. Harapan Ark Internusa Banjarmasin.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusions above, the authors provide suggestions and recommendations as follows:

- To improve and maintain Customer Satisfaction and to prevent the company from losses caused by the decrease in the level of customer satisfaction caused by the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) that is not suitable, the company needs to create an efficient system or tool that can improve Operational Employee Coordination and Operational Performance.
- To other researchers who will conduct research on Employee Coordination, Operational Performance, Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) and Customer Satisfaction, it is recommended to examine other variables that also have a significant influence. So it is hoped that these studies can be useful in providing input and recommendations to companies and the academic world.

IMPLICATION

Based on the conclusions of the research results and recommendations that have been described above, the implication is that Employee Coordination and Operational Performance in increasing the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) is getting better, communication both formal and non-formal can run according to the objectives, the use of several communication media has been used to facilitate the flow of information quickly and precisely. Decreases and errors in the Productivity of Coal Loading and Unloading Equipment (Conveyor) can be minimized, although problems in each process cannot be avoided, with good Operational Employee Coordination and Operational Performance, whatever problems arise will immediately get a solution to avoid disruption of coal loading and unloading.

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